

This is an activity to show A1/A2 level students how to look for common adjective + noun collocations using English Profile and COCA and to become familiar with the word *collocation*. Some A2 level words are included. It might be a challenging activity for A1 students, however the meanings are quite intuitive when viewed as opposites to adjectives they may well be familiar with already.

Given the digital competencies required and the familiarity with collocations in students' L1, it might be a more challenging activity for young learners (but I am open to anyone's opinion on this!)

It is an extension of a teaching idea I saw in **The Lexical Approach** by Michael Lewis where he suggested teaching the word *heavy* using lexical chunks/collocations like *heavy rain* and *heavy suitcase*. Students could do the same (but not always) for the opposite adjective for example *light rain* and *light suitcase*.

Activity for Students.

Example 1:

Look at these four adjectives: **difficult, hard, easy, soft**

Soft (A2) might be a new word. Let's (look up (B1) or confirm (B2)) check the meaning in our dictionary.

Now, let's make a chain of the four adjectives with their opposite adjective (*big – small, hot – cold, etc.*)

First,

difficult – hard? These can mean the same thing.

difficult – soft? These are not usually (A2) opposites (A2).

difficult – **easy**? This is okay.

Next,

easy – soft? These are not usually opposites.

easy – difficult? Okay, but we already have difficult – easy.

easy – **hard**? This is okay.

Finally,

hard – **soft**. This is okay.

So, our chain is **difficult – easy – hard – soft**

English Profile:

Okay, now let's go to <https://www.englishprofile.org/>

Let's click on **English Vocabulary profile**

The screenshot shows the English Profile website. The header is dark blue with the 'EnglishProfile' logo and 'The CEFR for English' tagline. A search bar is in the top right. The navigation menu on the left includes: Home, About Us (Corpus), The CEFR, English Vocabulary Profile (highlighted with a blue arrow), English Grammar Profile, Other Resources, and Contact Us. The main content area is titled 'English Profile – what the CEFR means for English' and contains text explaining the CEFR and the English Vocabulary Profile tool.

Let's click EVP Online

English Vocabulary Profile

The English Vocabulary Profile offers reliable information about which words (and importantly, which meanings of those words) and phrases are known and used by learners at each level of the [Common European Framework \(CEF\)](#).

Cambridge University Press is making the A1-C2 English Vocabulary Profile available free of charge to teachers and educationalists around the world. Go to [EVP Online](#) to access the resource.

Much more than a list of words!

The English Vocabulary Profile contains information about phrases, idioms and collocations as well as the words themselves. By leaving the text box blank and selecting one of the levels, you can generate lists of words for each level; but you can also filter these using the advanced search functions, to find out what 'food and drink' vocabulary A1 learners know, or which phrasal verbs are known at B2 level.

Let's type 'soft' into the search and let's click on 'Details' for soft = NOT HARD

English Vocabulary Profile Online - British English

A screenshot of the search results page for "soft". The search bar contains "soft". Below the search bar are filters for "Topic" and "Part of Speech". The results table has columns for "Base Word", "Guideword", "Level", "Part of Speech", "Topic", and "Details". A blue arrow points to the "Details" button for the entry "soft" with the level "B1".

Base Word	Guideword	Level	Part of Speech	Topic	Details
soft	GENTLE	B1	adjective		Details
soft	SMOOTH	A2	adjective	describing things	Details
soft	NOT HARD	A2	adjective	describing things	Details
soft drink		A2	noun	food and drink	Details
have a soft spot for sb/sth	IDIOM	C2	phrase		Details
have a soft spot for sb/sth	IDIOM	C2	phrase		Details

Let's click on '+' to see more

A screenshot of the word details page for "soft". The word is shown as "soft" with a pronunciation icon and "/sɒft/". Below the word are sections for "Word family", "soft (NOT HARD)", "soft (SMOOTH)", "soft (GENTLE)", and "have a soft spot for sb/sth". A blue arrow points to the "+" icon next to "soft (NOT HARD)".

soft • adjective /sɒft/

[Back to Report](#) [Full view](#)

+ Word family

+ **soft (NOT HARD)**
A2 not hard or firm

+ **soft (SMOOTH)**
A2 smooth and pleasant to touch

+ **soft (GENTLE)**
B1 not forceful, loud or easily noticed

+ **have a soft spot for sb/sth**
C2 to like someone or something a lot

Let's look at some examples of soft + noun **collocations** (*soft ground, soft pillow, soft cheese, soft centres*)
Soft **collocates** with *ground* and *pillow* and *cheese*. *Soft ground* is an adjective + noun **collocation**.

The screenshot shows the Cambridge Dictionary entry for the word 'soft'. At the top, it is labeled 'soft · adjective' with a speaker icon and the phonetic transcription '/soft/'. There are two buttons: 'Back to Report' and 'Full view'. Below the word, there is a 'Word family' section. The main section is titled 'soft (NOT HARD)' and includes a definition: 'not hard or firm'. A blue box highlights the 'Dictionary examples' section, which lists: 'soft ground', 'a soft pillow', 'soft cheese', and 'I like chocolates with soft centres.' A large blue arrow points from this box to the left. Below the examples is a 'Learner example' with the sentence: 'It's a small pillow. Oh, it's so soft and I never sleep without it. (Key English Test; A2; Portuguese)'. There are also sections for 'soft (SMOOTH)' and 'soft (GENTLE)' with their respective definitions.

Now, let's do the same for the other three adjectives.

We can see some examples of difficult + noun, easy + noun, hard + noun **collocations**.

Example 2:

Now, let's make a chain for these adjectives: **light, bright (A2), heavy(A2), dark**

Heavy (A2) might be a new word. Let's (look up (B1) or confirm (B2)) check the meaning in our dictionary.

Bright (A2) might be a new word. Let's (look up (B1) or confirm (B2)) check the meaning in our dictionary.

Follow the steps from Example 1 and make a chain.

So, our chain is **heavy – light – dark – bright**

English Profile:

Let's go to EVP Online in <https://www.englishprofile.org/>

Let's type 'heavy' into the search and let's click on 'Details' for heavy = WEIGHING A LOT

The screenshot shows the homepage of the English Profile website. The header is dark blue with the 'EnglishProfile' logo in white and 'The CEFR for English' below it. A search bar is in the top right. The main content area is white with a navigation menu on the left and a main heading 'English Profile – what the CEFR means for English'. Below the heading, there are three paragraphs of text explaining the website's purpose and the CEFR framework. The first paragraph states that English Profile helps teachers and educationalists understand the CEFR. The second paragraph lists the website's tools: English Vocabulary Profile Online and English Grammar Profile Online. The third paragraph mentions the project's support by the Council of Europe and the University of Cambridge.

Home ▾

The CEFR ▾

English Vocabulary Profile ▾

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- Compiling the EVP
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- FAQs
- Text Inspector

English Vocabulary Profile

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English Vocabulary Profile Online - British English

A1
A2
B1
B2
C1
C2
Select All

Topic

Part of Speech

Hide culturally sensitive words Yes

Category

Grammar

Usage

Prefix

Suffix

Results 1 - 4 of 4

Sort by:

Base Word	Guideword	Level	Part of Speech	Topic	Details
heavy	FORCE	C2	adjective		Details
heavy	A LOT	B1	adjective	describing things	Details
heavy	HOW MUCH	A2	adjective	describing things	Details
heavy	WEIGHING A LOT	A2	adjective	describing things	Details

[Back to Report](#)

heavy · *adjective* /'hevi/

[Full view](#)

+ heavy (WEIGHING A LOT)

A2 Heavy objects weigh a lot.

+ heavy (HOW MUCH)

A2 used to ask how much someone or something weighs

+ heavy (A LOT)

B1 large in amount or degree

+ heavy (FORCE)

C2 using a lot of force

heavy · adjective /hevi/

- heavy (WEIGHING A LOT)

A2 Heavy objects weigh a lot.

Dictionary examples:
 heavy **equipment**
 heavy **bags/suitcases**

Learner example:
 My phone is awesome. It is very small and I like it because it isn't heavy and I can listen to music with it. (Key English Test; A2; Spanish)

+ heavy (HOW MUCH)

A2 used to ask how much someone or something weighs

+ heavy (A LOT)

B2 large in amount or degree

+ heavy (FORCE)

C2 using a lot of force

We can see *heavy equipment* and *heavy bags/suitcases*. Now, let's do the same for the other three adjectives. We can see some examples of light + noun, dark + noun, bright + noun **collocations**.

Now, let's look at some adjectives + nouns which go together using another website.

English-Corpora:

Okay, now let's go to <https://www.english-corpora.org/>
 Let's click on Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA).

The screenshot shows the English-Corpora.org website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links: home, corpora, users, related resources, my account, upgrade, help. Below the navigation bar, there is a section titled "The most widely used online corpora." followed by a list of corpora. A blue arrow points to the "Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA)" row in the table.

Corpus (online access)	Download	# words	Dialect	Time period	Genre(s)
iWeb: The Intelligent Web-based Corpus		14 billion	6 countries	2017	Web
News on the Web (NOW)		12.1 billion+	20 countries	2010-yesterday	Web: News
Global Web-Based English (GloWbE)		1.9 billion	20 countries	2012-13	Web (incl blogs)
Wikipedia Corpus		1.9 billion	(Various)	2014	Wikipedia
Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA)		billions	American	1990-2019	Balanced
Coronavirus Corpus		897 million+	20 countries	Jan 2020-yesterday	Web: News
Corpus of Historical American English (COHA)		400 million	American	1810-2009	Balanced
The TV Corpus		325 million	6 countries	1950-2018	TV shows
The Movie Corpus		200 million	6 countries	1930-2018	Movies
Corpus of American Soap Operas		100 million	American	2001-2012	TV shows

Let's click on '+' to see more options.

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH FREQUENCY CONTEXT OVERVIEW

List Chart Word Browse +

[POS]?

Find matching strings Reset

Sections Texts/Virtual Sort/Limit Options

(HIDE HELP) NOT LOGGED IN

Download the corpus (and corpus-based frequency data) for offline use

The Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) is the only **large**, genre-balanced corpus of American English. COCA is probably the **most widely-used corpus of English**, and it is related to many other **corpora of English** that we have created, which offer unparalleled insight into **variation in English**.

The corpus contains more than **one billion words** of text (25+ million words each year 1990-2019) from eight genres: spoken, fiction, popular magazines, newspapers, academic texts, and (with the **update in March 2020**): TV and Movies subtitles, blogs, and other web pages.

Click on any of the links in the search form to the left for context-sensitive help, and to see the range of queries that the corpus offers.

There are four main ways to search the corpus:

First, you can **browse a frequency list** of the top 60,000 words in the corpus, including searches by word form, part of speech, ranges in the 60,000 word list, and even by meaning or pronunciation. This should be particularly useful for language learners and teachers.

Second, you can **search by individual word**, and see collocates, topics, clusters,

Let's click on **Collocates**.

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH FREQUENCY CONTEXT OVERVIEW

List Chart Word Browse **Collocates**

[POS]?

Find matching strings Reset

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We can see Word/phrase and **Collocates**.

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH FREQUENCY CONTEXT OVERVIEW

List Chart Word Browse **Collocates** Compare KWIC -

Word/phrase []

Collocates [POS]

+ 4 3 2 1 0 0 1 2 3 4 +

Find collocates Reset

Sections Texts/Virtual Sort/Limit Options

(HIDE HELP) NOT LOGGED IN

COLLOCATES display

To find collocates in COCA, you would normally input a word via **Word**, and then select Collocates on the next page. In COCA, the collocates display (via **Word**) is much better than with the other corpora from English-Corpora.org, such as automatically grouping collocates by part of speech. Some examples: **bread, kiss (v), rough, or naturally**.

The only time that you'd want to use the form to the left is when you want to find collocates for a string of words (e.g. **put away** or **fire station**), or when you absolutely need to limit the number of words left or right.

Note however that using the form to the left for individual words (especially high frequency words) will be *much* slower, and in many cases the search will "time out", resulting in an error. In nearly all cases, it is much better to search for collocates via **Word**.

See what words occur near other words, which provides great insight into meaning and usage. For example, nouns after **thick** or **look into**, verbs before **money**, or any word near **crack, believe, loud, or quickly**.

More information: [compare to LIST display](#), [types of collocates](#), [direction](#), and

Let's type 'heavy' into Word/Phrase

List Chart Word Browse **Collocates** Compare KWIC -

heavy Word/phrase

Collocates [POS]

+ 4 3 2 1 0 0 1 2 3 4 +

Find collocates Reset

Sections Texts/Virtual Sort/Limit Options

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Let's click on Collocates POS. We can see 'Insert POS'.

List Chart Word Browse **Collocates** Compare KWIC -

heavy Word/phrase [POS] ?

Collocates Insert PoS

+ 4 3 2 1 0 0 1 2 3 4 +

Find collocates Reset

Sections Texts/Virtual Sort/Limit Options

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Let's click on Insert POS and select nounALL

List Chart Word Browse **Collocates** Compare KWIC -

heavy Word/phrase [POS] ?

Collocates Insert PoS

- noun.ALL
- verb.ALL
- adj.ALL
- adv.ALL
-
- neg.ALL
- art.ALL
- det.ALL
- pron.ALL
- poss.ALL
- prep.ALL
- conj.ALL
- interj.ALL
- punc.ALL
-
- noun.ALL+
- noun.SG
- noun.PL
- noun.CMN
- noun.+PROP
-

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See what words occur near other words, which provides great insight into meaning and usage. For example, nouns after *thick* or *look into*, verbs before *money*, or any word near *crack, believe, loud, or quickly*.

Now, the corpus will search for heavy+NOUN collocates.

SEARCH FREQUENCY CONTEXT OVERVIEW

List Chart Word Browse **Collocates** Compare KWIC -

heavy Word/phrase [POS] ?
 NOUN Collocates noun.ALL

+ 4 3 2 1 0 0 1 2 3 4 +
 Find collocates Reset

Sections Texts/Virtual Sort/Limit Options

(HIDE HELP) NOT LOGGED IN

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More information: [access to LFT display type of collocates direction and](#)

We can see the results for heavy+NOUN collocates.

SEARCH WORD CONTEXT OVERVIEW

COLLOCATES **HEAVY** ADJ See also

NOUN Advanced options Collocates Clusters Topics Dictionary Texts KWIC

+ NOUN	NEW WORD	?
2619	6.36	metal
2445	6.12	rain
1227	5.46	cream
1071	5.90	load
1000	5.74	burden
997	3.98	weight
976	8.72	lifting
837	4.86	snow
829	4.57	equipment
760	4.43	traffic
637	3.16	weapon
596	2.60	industry
564	3.09	bag
561	3.37	wind
547	3.35	element
545	5.36	drinking

NEW WORD	?
3.88	thick
3.03	light
4.07	wooden
3.54	wet
6.10	bulky
7.4	episodic
4.2	bleeding
2.96	moderate
8.08	whipping
3.16	toxic
5.37	medium-high
3.61	dense
3.42	crude
3.06	stiff
2.54	awkward
2.84	rubber
2.89	sour

+ VERB	NEW WORD	?
1091	3.22	carry
584	3.94	lift
264	3.72	weigh
200	2.59	bear
145	3.86	cup
119	3.85	haul
117	4.54	inflict
107	3.59	whip
87	3.19	rain
84	5.86	lug
76	3.04	heat
67	5.77	exact
39	2.56	pound
35	3.88	shoulder
32	3.82	burden
31	2.99	withstand
27	2.94	incur
25	2.67	drape

+ ADV	NEW WORD	?
236	2.87	under
76	4.20	unusually
68	3.29	open
27	3.36	moderately
27	3.86	eg
25	2.58	ie
22	2.93	preferably
19	3.56	noticeably
18	3.66	impossibly
17	2.60	c
10	2.81	inward
10	2.86	excessively
10	4.75	unbearably
9	2.64	marginally
8	3.64	abnormally
5	2.51	absurdly
5	5.71	oppressively

We can see 1. heavy metal, 2. heavy rain, 3. heavy cream, etc., and we can see that these often go together.

Now, let's do the same for *light* + NOUN, *dark* + NOUN, *bright* + NOUN.

Can you make a sentence for each *adjective* + NOUN collocation?

Examples:

1. When there is heavy rain, I take the subway. (A1 AmE / B2 BrE)
2. I like to walk in light rain. A1

Are there any adjectives with the same noun? Can we make a chain?

SEARCH

COLLOCATES **HEAVY** **ADJ** See also: [ADV](#) [NOUN](#)

+ NOUN	NEW WORD	?
2619 6.36	metal	
2445 6.12	rain	
1227 5.46	cream	
1071 5.90	load	
1000 5.74	burden	
997 3.98	weight	
976 8.72	lifting	
837 4.86	snow	
829 4.57	equipment	
760 4.43	traffic	
637 3.16	weapon	
596 2.60	industry	
564 3.09	bag	
561 3.37	wind	
547 3.35	element	
545 5.36	drinking	
504 2.92	cup	
483 2.63	loss	
476 3.62	pound	
437 6.79	artillery	

SEARCH

COLLOCATES **LIGHT** **ADJ** See also: [ADV](#) [NOUN](#)

+ NOUN	NEW WORD	?
1218 6.88	rail	
1003 3.53	color	
948 3.47	source	
903 4.16	weight	
814 3.31	hair	
649 7.86	fixture	
611 4.47	sugar	
568 3.63	skin	
555 3.82	truck	
540 3.95	speed	
525 4.65	touch	
496 4.14	rain	
453 3.09	cup	
452 5.46	pollution	
393 5.07	shade	
384 3.56	wave	
338 3.87	snow	
337 5.39	beam	
334 4.30	green	
328 2.92	wind	

SEARCH

COLLOCATES **DARK** **ADJ** See also: [ADV](#) [NOUN](#)

+ NOUN	NEW WORD	?
4901 5.04	hair	
4438 3.67	side	
4341 3.57	eye	
2951 4.07	matter	
1666 4.61	sky	
1640 7.75	knight	
1586 4.29	skin	
1515 2.78	age	
1352 3.10	energy	
1267 4.80	cloud	
1260 3.04	color	
1244 2.71	light	
1038 3.80	corner	
1009 4.50	shadow	
1004 4.12	suit	
948 4.94	chocolate	
863 3.16	glass	
848 3.80	wood	
743 3.38	horse	
739 4.65	green	

SEARCH

COLLOCATES **BRIGHT** **ADJ** See also: [ADV](#) [NOUN](#)

+ NOUN	NEW WORD	?
4037 5.21	light	
2626 4.77	star	
2186 4.63	color	
2183 3.37	eye	
2121 4.58	future	
1898 3.24	side	
1456 5.06	spot	
1229 4.40	sun	
1127 6.08	red	
950 4.59	sky	
599 5.13	green	
580 4.20	moon	
500 6.07	sunlight	
462 3.81	smile	
378 3.24	object	
377 5.15	orange	
308 5.25	magnitude	
297 3.28	flower	
287 2.80	planet	
278 4.27	galaxy	

Example chain: heavy snow
 light snow
 light color
 dark color
 bright color
 bright?
 heavy?

We can see bright object. If we go down the page we can see heavy object.

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH WORD CONTEXT OVERVIEW

COLLOCATES **HEAVY** **ADJ** See also as: [ADV](#) [NOUN](#) Advanced options

+ NOUN	NEW WORD	?
2619 6.36	metal	
2445 6.12	rain	
1227 5.46	cream	
1071 5.90	load	
1000 5.74	burden	
997 3.98	weight	
976 8.72	lifting	
837 4.86	snow	
829 4.57	equipment	
760 4.43	traffic	
637 3.16	weapon	
596 2.60	industry	
564 3.09	bag	
561 3.37	wind	
547 3.35	element	
545 5.36	drinking	
504 2.92	cup	
483 2.63	loss	
476 3.62	pound	
437 6.79	artillery	
410 6.36	machinery	
384 2.77	heat	
380 6.21	hitter	
376 4.72	fighting	
371 3.32	duty	
370 4.79	dose	
364 7.02	rainfall	
361 5.38	breathing	
356 4.05	boot	
355 2.57	user	
348 2.81	object	
336 6.85	saucepan	

+ Adj	NEW WORD	?
397 3.88	thick	
352 3.03	light	
257 4.07	wooden	
229 3.54	wet	
135 6.10	bulky	
132 7.45	episodic	
131 3.68	medium	
125 4.52	bleeding	
105 2.96	moderate	
101 8.08	whipping	
93 3.16	toxic	
85 5.37	medium-high	
84 3.61	dense	
76 3.42	crude	
66 3.06	stiff	
63 2.54	awkward	
49 2.84	rubber	
44 2.89	sour	
44 6.17	woolen	
43 2.66	dull	
42 5.11	menstrual	
40 4.98	cumbersome	
39 3.91	armored	
34 5.95	relativistic	
31 3.07	lamb	
30 3.05	laden	
28 3.35	clumsy	
28 4.02	humid	
27 3.18	cardboard	
25 3.55	stainless	
22 3.00	unwieldy	
17 3.97	durable	

+ VERB	NEW WORD	?
1091 3.22	carry	
584 3.94	lift	
264 3.72	weigh	
200 2.59	bear	
145 3.86	cup	
119 3.85	haul	
117 4.54	inflict	
107 3.59	whip	
87 3.19	rain	
84 5.86	lug	
76 3.04	heat	
67 5.77	exact	
39 2.56	pound	
35 3.88	shoulder	
32 3.82	burden	
31 2.99	withstand	
27 2.94	incur	
25 2.67	drape	
25 3.48	hoist	
24 2.73	contaminate	
24 3.71	weight	
20 3.11	heave	
18 2.98	sag	
17 3.47	levy	
13 2.54	sling	
13 2.58	lace	
11 3.12	creak	
10 3.03	drench	
10 3.61	pelt	
9 2.88	shroud	
9 3.00	tote	
8 3.68	mortar	

+ ADV	NEW WORD	?
236 2.87	under	
76 4.20	unusually	
68 3.29	open	
27 3.36	moderately	
27 3.86	eg	
25 2.58	ie	
22 2.93	preferably	
19 3.56	noticeably	
18 3.66	impossibly	
17 2.60	c	
10 2.81	inward	
10 2.86	excessively	
10 4.75	unbearably	
9 2.64	marginally	
8 3.64	abnormally	
5 2.51	absurdly	
5 5.71	oppressively	

1. Using COCA, can you find adjective + noun **collocations** for : **difficult, easy, hard, soft**?
2. Can you make any chains with **difficult + noun, easy + noun, hard, + noun, soft + noun**?
3. Let's write a sentence for each **collocation**.

We can think of seven main types of **collocation** in sentences:

- adjective + noun.
- adverb + adjective.
- noun + noun.
- noun + verb.
- verb + noun.
- verb + expression with preposition.
- verb + adverb.

Today, we looked at

adjective + noun **collocations**

such as *heavy rain*,
light snow, *dark hair*,
bright future (B1),
etc.

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